

Impacts of Social Networking Site (SNS) on Growing up Adolescent Girls: A study on Bangladeshi Collegiate Girls School in Khulna

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Accepted Mar 18, 2021
Published Mar 21, 2021

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4625075>

Pages: 112-127

Funding: No

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How to cite this article (APA):
Taherun Nesa Suborna., &
Nuruddin Ahmed Masud. (2021).
Impacts of Social Networking
Site (SNS) on Growing up
Adolescent Girls: A study on
Bangladeshi Collegiate Girls
School in Khulna. *North
American Academic Research*,
4(3), 112-127. doi:
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4625075>

ABSTRACT

Nowadays the internet has gained paramount importance in the education arena. The main objective of the study is to identify the impacts of social networking sites (SNS) on growing up adolescent girls in KCC. To identify the nature of browsing the internet, to find out how social sites help to increase the knowledge level, to know the impact of using a social networking site. The study was conducted through a survey research design. For this study, purposive sampling was used. Samples were collected from the 13 to 18-year girls. The total sample size was 100. The average age of using the internet for the first time of the respondents was 17.71 years old. The study shows that teenagers were positively affected as social media helped in increasing their communication abilities, getting information, developing their technical skills, and how they can effectively use this recent technology.

KEYWORDS: SOCIAL NETWORKING SITE, ADOLESCENT GIRLS, INTERNET BROWSING, PERSONAL ACTIVITY, ACADEMIC ACTIVITY.

Introduction

Social networking site like Facebook has become a part of the daily life experiences for an increasing number of people. Therefore, Facebook is a web-based service which is allowing individual youth or teenagers to construct a public profile in a bounded system. Therefore, this social networking site helps an individual to share connections, views, thoughts with strangers (unknown friends) or enable to share their viewpoints with

visible well-known friend. Most commonly used are connecting with existing networks, making and developing friendships, create an online presence for their users, viewing content, finding information, creating and customizing profiles, and so on (Smith, 2011).

The nature and nomenclature of these connections may vary from one social networking site to another site. A brainstorming effect is developing among the youth, that this can maintain their privacy and for that purpose which can share their societal information only in front of well-known friends whereas others are not able to access that information. Therefore, besides accessing the information firstly people should send the friend request to their friends (known or unknown) and if the other side will accept the sending friend request, then abounded social profile might be formed and that is more important while anyone can join in this social networking circle. In this way, anyone can cascade their privacy on personal space in front of online readers and strangers and becoming popular among the youth. However, while it has been discussed its negative side, positively this social networking site performs the various type of cybercrimes which lead to demotivate the young generations and sometimes it might be involved into various unprofessional or illegal works which are considered to be negative feedback of this site (Tamir & Mitchell, 2012). However, through this research paper, it can be pointed out the status of social media and how it may affect among the young generations in Bangladesh.

Statement of the Problem

Teenagers these days widely use social networks (sites). These have made this a part of their daily activities. Every webpage that allows for social interaction is considered to be a social media site. Many scholars suggest that students learn in new ways using social media and that educators should embrace these new platforms (Ito et al., 2009; Jenkins, 2006). For example, Facebook and similar social media programs allow students to gather outside of class for the purpose of collaborating and exchanging ideas about assignments (O'Keeffe, G.S. & Clarke-Pearson, K., 2011). Unique features of interactivity and connectedness are the key success factors for SNS which give users a feeling of staying in touch and closeness. As people are getting closer virtually and spending more time online, offline relationships with family and friends are getting less attention and that's how SNS is affecting human relationships negatively. Over time SNS users have developed positive perceptions regarding trust issues on SNS which is also accelerating the negative impact of SNS on human relationships. American Pew Research Center's study found that an SNS user who uses the site multiple times per day is 43% more likely than other internet users. While SNS users are earning the trust of other users virtually, too much addiction to SNS is creating a lack of trust issue in real-life relationships (Ceyhan, 2011). So, there has been a great deal of speculation regarding the positivity and negativity of using social networking sites and therefore it's essential to perform further research to identify and measure whether the positive or negative effects outweigh the opposite, and only then it will be possible to put a firm statement regarding the effects of using social networking site on adolescents' study and their family life.

Review of Literature

In this world of modern science and advanced technology, communication has become a very easy and simple thing throughout the world. Earlier were sending mail to a distant place or country or even to the other side of the earth took months to reach, now is possible within a moment with the touch of our tip of fingers. With the advancement and enhancement of the internet, computer, laptop and specially Smartphone, social media have become an inevitable part of this generation. But as it is known every action has an opposite reaction, likewise besides several benefits there is emerged some negative effects as well. This generation has become dependent focused more on virtual life than their practical life. These are always busy with social media activities in Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, Telegram, WhatsApp, and so on internet-based social media with showoffs, selfies, etc. However, practically these are becoming more unsocial to their surroundings, unfriendly and rude to their friends and family, disrespectful to the laws, rules, and regulations, and inattentive to their studies. For example, researchers have indicated “Selfie” (to a large extent) as a mentally disordered action.

June Ahn (2011) conducted a study entitled ‘The Effect of Social Network Sites on Adolescents’ Social and Academic Development: Current Theories and Controversies’ Teenagers are among the most prolific users of social network sites (SNS). Elda Tartari (2015) examined a paper entitled Benefits and Risks of Children and Adolescents Using Social Media. The researcher explained that Children and teenagers widely use social media, and recent studies have shown that they spend the majority of their time daily on social media pages. He also focused on the positive and negative impacts that social media has on the development of teenagers. The selected age was 11-16 those were selected as regular users of social media. The study shows that children and teenagers were positively affected as social media helped in increasing their communication abilities, getting information, developing their technical skills, and how this can effectively use this recent technology. On the other side, these are exposed to the risk of Facebook depression, cyberbullying, and online sexual harassment

Al-Jubayer (2013) entitled a paper ‘The Use of Social Networking Sites among Teenagers: A Study of Facebook Use in Dhaka City. This study is an attempt to understand some of the issues involved in Bangladesh teenagers and the use of Facebook. One hundred subjects aged 12 to 18 years residing in Dhaka city were interviewed on their use of Facebook and its impact on daily life. The most common social networking sites include Facebook, Twitter, WhatsApp, and LinkedIn among others. It spending a lot of time on their mobile phones accessing the (SNSs) at the expense of going out to find friends to interact with face to face.

Keith N. Hampton (2011) conducted research entitled Social networking sites and our lives under Pew Research Center’s Internet & American Life Project. The researcher collected data from a survey conducted by American Life Project. The study assessed how peoples’ political and civic involvement, personal relationships, and trust are interconnected with their use of technologies and social networking platforms such as SNS. This study also tried to find out whether these social networking sites were helping people to stay connected or isolating them from non-virtual relationships. Necessary data were collected from college students through a questionnaire that assessed the respondents’ social media habits, communication manners,

and how it affects their self-concept. The study also assessed the students' social media communication skills with friends and family and how those skills affect their relationships. Tham and Ahmed (2011) directed a study entitled the usage and implications of social networking sites: A survey of college students. Researchers performed the survey with a non-random sample of 445 college students to assess the level of correlation among their usage of social networking sites, personal development, and academic performance. The study revealed that with the increase in age level, the time spent on social networking sites decreases, and female students spend more time for social networking compared to their male counterparts. Results also revealed that the level of usage of social networking sites has a negative impact on students' academic performance.

Sonja and Camiel (2011) have conducted a study entitled The Role of Social Network Sites in Romantic Relationships: Effects on Jealousy and Relationship Happiness. The authors performed an online survey where 138 females and 194 male students of a Dutch University who were involved in romantic relationships responded to the survey questionnaire. The study examined the complex correlations among the use of SNS, self-esteem, need for popularity, trait jealousy, relationship satisfaction, and some other closely related issues. The study revealed that the feelings of jealousy among students have been increased to a great extent by SNS and trait jealousy mainly determines SNS jealousy where time spent on SNS is a crucial consideration.

Pantic et al. (2012) published a research paper entitled 'Association between online social networking and depression in high school students: Behavioral psychology viewpoint.' Researchers found that the relationship between depression and total time spent on SNS by students is positively correlated. Rosen et al. (2013) in this study found that students who spend more time on SNS and perform more image management are subject to more clinical symptoms of depression. Results also revealed a similar positive correlation between increased social media use and decreased academic performance of students. Elda Tartari (2015) examined a paper entitled Benefits and Risks of Children and Adolescents Using Social Media. The researcher explained that Children and teenagers widely use social media, and recent studies have shown that they spend a majority of their time daily on social media pages. He also focused on the positive and negative impacts that social media has on the development of teenagers.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study is to identify the impacts of social networking sites (SNS) on growing up adolescent girls.

- To identify the nature of browsing the internet;
- To find out how social sites help to increase the knowledge level; and
- To analyze the impact of using a social networking site.

Research Question

- What is the Impact of Social Networking Site on Growing up Adolescent Girls?
 - a) Impacts of Internet on Personal Activity.
 - b) Impacts of Internet on Academic Activity.

Methodology

The methodology is the philosophical evaluation of investigative techniques within a discipline: a concern with the conceptual, theoretical, and research aspects of knowledge (Jary and Jary, 2000). It is a systematic way to solve the research problem (Kothari, 2004). A method involved a process in which various stages of collecting data or information are explained and the analytical techniques are defined. It may be understood as a science of how research is done scientifically (Kothari, 2004). For the good accomplishment of research work, a well-arranged methodology is extremely needed (Raj, 1988).

Nature of the Study

The research was descriptive in nature. Descriptive research deals with survey and fact-finding queries of different kinds and it tries to describe the impacts of social networking sites (SNS) on growing up adolescent girls.

Method of the Study

The method is a systematic system that is definite and common to all social scientists (Raj, 1988). To conduct this study social survey method was followed as it enables quick investigation for large numbers of cases and its result have wide applicability (Johnson and Onwuegbuzie, 2004.) Social surveys help to find out the problem of social disorganization, the explanation for a social problem, and to test hypothesis social investigators can then explain a social phenomenon with some confidence and authenticity (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2007). The study was conducted through a survey research design. Survey research is one of the most important areas of measurement in applied social research. The broad area of survey research encompasses any measurement procedures that involve asking questions of respondents.

Study Area

To describe the actual scenario, this present study is carefully driven in the 'Khulna' district of Bangladesh. The main focus was on the Khulna collegiate girl's school and KCC Women's College. The study area was purposively selected. Khulna collegiate girl's school was established in 1996.

Unit of Analysis

Unit of Analysis refers to the level of aggregation of the data, collected during the subsequent data analysis stage. To achieve the study objective, some specifications were made to identify the interviewees, e.g. (i) The age of adolescent girls 13 to 19 (ii) Studying in the aforementioned School.

Population of the Study

Population, simply, is the aggregate of individuals or items from which a sample is drawn (Jary and Jary, 2000). In other words, “it is the whole population, out of which sample is selected” (Raj, 1996). According to the aforementioned criteria, an informal cause was carried out to identify the population of the study, and 150 girls were identified as the population of the study.

Sampling Procedure

Sampling is the selection procedure of a representative portion of the total population, with its logic and basic techniques (Jary and Jary, 2000). For this study, purposive sampling was used. The sample was collected from the criteria girls. The total samples were 100. Data as such is nothing else, but a mass of information and that is the reason that every research should be conscious of collecting such data, which were needed actually (Raj, 1988). Primary data was collected through the interview schedule. It was conducted following a questionnaire which is prepared and checked earlier by the supervisor and then fills those up by a face to face conversations with the respondents. In the primary data, information included demographic information of respondents as well as other basic information which covers the general study for assessing impacts of social media. Secondary data are the data that have been interpreted and recorded.

A major aspect of using secondary data is assessing the quality of the information or opinions provided. It is also good practice to compare the data from different sources. This will help to identify bias, inaccuracies, and pure imagination (Walliamson, 2005). In this study booklets, pamphlets, and brochures from the below department such as-local NGO, BBS, FAO, books, journals, articles, newspapers, unpolished reports, and so on are used to give the study a logical background.

Techniques of Data Collection

Technique means a procedure that aims at helping knowledge getting systematized (Raj, 1988). An interview Schedule is a method of collecting social data at the individual level which ensures a higher response rate than any other method of data collection (Jary and Jary, 2000). An interview schedule is prepared which contained both open and close-ended items and then data was collected by the interviewer herself with the particular respondent through face-to-face conversation regarding the impact of social media-related questions.

Development of Study Instrument(s)

An interview schedule was developed primarily and given to the supervisor for correction. The corrected interview schedule was primarily used for data collection through a pre-test. Some needed editing and problems were identified during the pre-test. The problems as identified during the pre-test interview schedule were corrected with the suggestion of the supervisor and then finally corrected interview schedule was finally

used for data collection from the field.

Results

Analysis of data refers to studying the tabulated data to determine inherent facts or meaning. It includes the breaking down of existing complex factors into simpler parts and putting the parts together in new arrangements for interpretation (Saravanvel, 1992). After collecting and analyzing the data, the researcher had to accomplish the task of drawing inferences followed by report writing. Processed data were analyzed and interpret regarding the objectives of the study. The whole analysis and interpretation held to develop a written research report with the major findings. A draft report is prepared and given to the proper authority for comments and suggestions. According to the suggestion, the draft report is being revised and finalized and then, it was submitted to the authority.

Age Distribution

Different age group is an important factor to understand different social phenomena in different circumstances of the adolescent's girls. Different age groups between 13 to below 19 were selected in the study. The distribution of respondents by age is given in the following table.

Table 1:age distribution of the respondent		
Response	Number of Respondents	Percent (%)
13-15	33	33.0
16-19	67	67.0
Total	100	100.0

(Field Survey, 2020)

The data, presented in the table 1 show that, majority of the respondents belonged to the age group between 16 to 19 years and the percentage is 67.0. 33.0 percent of them were at the age between 13 to 15 years. So, from the table shows that most of the girls of the study area were age 16-19 and this age is very vulnerable for directing to the wrong.

Religious Identity of the Respondents

Religion is an important thing for use the internet. There are various points of view in a particular religion that impacts the educational achievement of the student. Few religious beliefs inspire students to use the internet and some religious belief despairs the side effects of using the internet. Religious values play a vital role in the effect of internet knowledge. In the view of Islam, multimedia such as music, song, movie, pornography is restricted to enjoy. Pornography is a restricted issue for every religion. Therefore, it influences knowledge-seeking behavior.

Table 2: Religion of the Respondents		
Response	Number of Respondents	Percent (%)
Muslim	82	82.0
Hindu	14	14.0
Christian	4	4.0
Total	100	100.0

(Field Survey, 2020)

Table 2 implies the religious status of the respondents. Among the respondents about 82 percent were Muslim and 14 percent were Hindu. The rest of 4 percent was Christian religious of the respondents.

Marital Status of the Respondents

Marital status is the condition of being married or unmarried. Marital status impacts on use internet that also influences the achievement of students. It is generally thought that the people who are married can't spend much more time using the internet to gain more knowledge which can contribute to enhancing achievement.

Table 3: Marital Status of the Respondents		
Response	Number of Respondents	Percent (%)
Unmarried	88	88.0
Married	12	12.0
Total	100	100.0

(Field Survey, 2020)

Table 3 indicates the marital status of the respondents. Large amount of the respondent 88 percent was unmarried while only 12 percent were married.

Types of Family (Income)

The traditional family structure in the United States is considered a family support system involving two married individuals providing care and stability for their biological offspring. However, this two-parent, nuclear family has become less prevalent, and alternative family forms have become more common. The Single Income Family Supplement was paid to individuals where the main income earner has a taxable income. A dual-income family is a family that gets money from two separate incomes, such as an income from the father and mother.

Table 4: Types of Family (Income)		
Response	Number of Respondents	Percent (%)
Single income	71	71.0
Duel income family	29	29.0
Total	100	100.0

(Field Survey, 2020)

Table 4 represents the types of family based on income. About 71 percent family was single income family and the rest of 29 percent of the family were duel income family.

Information about the nature of internet browsing

About 56 percent of the respondents remembered they used their first internet at the age of 17-18. Another 18 percent started at the age ≤ 16 and the rest of 26 percent used internet since they were at age of $19 \geq$. The mean age was 17.71 years.

Learn of the browsing internet- means where from a person learn to use or access the internet. The highest 53 percent of the respondents learnt of using internet by own. 41 percent learnt from the help of friends and the rest of 6 percent learnt from their family members such as brothers or sisters to use internet.

Equipment for Using Internet- 37 percent of the respondents use laptop as their primary device for using internet. About 31 percent of the respondents used desktop and 28 percent used mobile phone for accessing internet. The rest of 4 percent of the respondents used tab for using internet.

Types of Data Connection- Package Using by the Respondents Mostly, more than half (87 percent) of the respondents used monthly pack from any operator for accessing internet. 6 percent used weekly pack and 4 percent preferred half monthly pack. Only 3 percent of the respondents used daily pack for accessing internet.

Purpose of using internet (Academic and Non-academic)

About 5 percent of the respondents used internet sometimes as their necessity, 71 percent of the respondents used very often and 18 percent often used internet. The rest of 3 percent of the respondents rarely used internet.

Main purposes for using internet of the respondents 53 percent used internet as their entertainment in leisure period. Another 30 percent emphasized on internet as their primary communication and the rest of 17 percent of the respondents used internet only their study purposes.

The response about browsing of educational sites regularly of the respondents, 8 percent actually visit internet website rarely for educational purposes while 67 percent sometimes did that. 14 percent often browsing educational sites and the rest small portion of 5 percent never browsing educational sites using internet.

The response about collection of educational materials from internet, surprisingly 2 percent of the respondents never collected any educational information from internet. 54 percent sometimes collecting information and 3 percent rarely. The rest of 25 percent of the respondents very often took their educational materials from internet.

The best site for educational purpose, 75 percent respondents agreed that Wikipedia is the best website for educational purposes. Only 6 percent said about Journals and 14 preferred Banglapedia as well. The rest of 3 percent liked Britannica Encyclopedia and 2 percent liked Microsoft Encarta for their educational purposes.

36 percent of the respondents were spending last week for gaining knowledge ≤ 12 hours weekly and 56 percent of the respondents were spending on the internet 13-18 hours weekly. 8 percent of the respondents were spending on the internet $19 \geq$ hours weekly and the average spending time of the respondents for gaining knowledge was 13.85 hours per week.

22 percent of the respondents were spending last week for Entertainment $21 \geq$ hours weekly and 48 percent of the respondents were spending on the internet 13-20 hours weekly. 30 percent of the respondents were spending on the internet ≤ 12 hours weekly and the average spending time of the respondents for entertainment was 16.01 hours per week.

Impacts of Internet on Personal Activity

Impact of internet on personal life of the respondents, more than half of 66 percent respondents said there had some positive or negative impact of internet on their personal life while 34 percent argued with that thinking.

Change of lifestyle following internet of the respondents, 57 percent responded that they had no change of lifestyle following internet. The rest of 43 percent respondents changed their lifestyle following internet in various ways.

Change of behavioral pattern because of internet of the respondents, 25 percent of the respondents thought their behavior was changing what they expect while 23 percent respondents observed their behavior as usual and that was noticeable for them. 35 percent remain unchanged and rest of 17 percent had no comment about this matter.

The opinion of the respondents about their using internet, surprisingly the highest 78 percent of the respondents thought internet has positive sides and negative sides as well as another 14 percent were positive and the rest of 8 percent of the respondents had negative opinion about the use of internet.

The response about internet is a waste of time, 43 percent of the respondents sometimes feel that internet is a waste of time while 22 percent very often realized that and 24 percent often. The rest of 9 percent thought internet is useful and not time killer for them.

Impacts of Internet on Academic Activity

Opinion of the respondents about the role of internet, about 60 percent respondents often think internet helps in their study while 26 percent felt that very often. Another 11 percent respondents sometimes felt the importance of internet in their study.

The willingness to pay extra cost for using internet, almost all the students that mean 93 percent students were willing to provide extra cost for internet. The rest 7 percent respondents were not agreed to provide extra cost

for internet. The health problem using internet. Almost all of the respondents; 83 percent faced that internet make them sick. Small portion of 17 percent were positive answer to use internet. Most of the respondent were faced health problem some of them were facing Insomnia (37%), some others faced tiredness (21%), a group of respondent faced short time memory loss (15%), besides the other problems that were also dangerous for health

Chi Square

First Age of Using Internet and impact of using internet

The impact of using the internet is different for the first age of browsing the internet of the respondent. Findings in Table 5 show that the first age of browsing the internet was dependent largely on the impact of using the internet and the differences are statistically significant ($p < .000$).

impact of using internet	First Age of Browsing Internet			Total
	≤ 16	17-18	$19 \geq$	
66	42	24	0	66 (100)
34	0	24	10	34 (100)
$\chi^2 = 45.143 (2); Monte Carlo^1 p < .000 (.01)$				
Fisher's Exact Test = 55.076				

Spending Time for Entertainment and impact of using internet

The impact of using the internet is different for spent last week for the entertainment of the respondent. Findings in Table 6 show that spent last week on entertainment was dependent largely on the impact of using the internet and the differences are statistically significant ($p < .000$).

Impact of using internet	Spent Last Week for Entertainment (RC)			Total
	Low	Medium	High	
66	12	18	36	66
34	6	18	10	34
$\chi^2 = 53.333 (2); Monte Carlo p < .000 (.01)$				
Fisher's Exact Test = 66.009				

According to the rules of IBM SPSS 20, Monte Carlo significance technique is performed in cases, where sample size were smaller/ no. of frequencies less than 5 in any cell of 3×3 table, to examine the significance of the association (contingency) between different independent and dependent variables (Wikipedia, 2015).

Discussion

The fabulous growth in telecommunication has brought online services, specialized electronic networks, Webpages, E-mail, software, and global information resources to our homes as well as to education. The average age of using the internet for the first time of the respondents was 17.71 years old. The highest 53 percent of the respondents learned of using the internet on their own. 41 percent learned with the help of friends and the rest of 6 percent learned from their family members such as brothers or sisters to use the internet. 37 percent of the respondents use the laptop as their primary device for using the internet. More than half (87 percent) of the respondents used a monthly pack from any operator for accessing the internet, 6 percent used a weekly pack and 4 percent preferred half monthly pack. The purpose of the internet is the identification of the cause of internet use, cause of taking connection and interest to the internet. To understand the purpose of internet browsing Mostly usage thing, communication information, entrance site, and daily activities issues were important determinants that influenced the academic and non-academic activities. More than half (53 percent) used the internet as their entertainment in the leisure period. Another 30 percent emphasized the internet as their primary communication and the rest of 17 percent of the respondents used the internet only for their study purposes. Only 8 percent actually visit internet websites rarely for educational purposes while 67 percent sometimes did that. 14 percent of the respondents often browse educationalists and the rest small portion of 5 percent never browsing educational sites. Surprisingly 2 percent of the respondents never collected any educational information from the internet, 54 percent sometimes collected information, and 3 percent rarely. The other 25 percent of the respondents very often took their educational materials from the internet. 40 percent of the respondents very often satisfied with the help/service of internet materials and 37 percent often satisfied while only 2 percent of respondents never satisfied. 75 percent of respondents considered Wikipedia as the best website for educational purposes. There are many files found on the internet both academic and non-academic. Study materials mean the source of study. The Internet is a good source of collecting materials. About 70 percent of the respondents used internet documents as their electronic resources for educational purposes whereas only 9 percent preferred various educational websites and 13 percent collecting their educational information by using E-books. 45 percent of respondents thought that the internet was the best way for gaining knowledge while only 16 percent preferred teachers as the best way for gaining knowledge. More than half (56 percent) of the respondents were spending on the internet 13-18 hours weekly and 8 percent of the respondents were spending on the internet 19 hours or more than that per week. The average spending time of the respondents for gaining knowledge was 13.85 hours per week.

The main purpose of the Internet is offering effective information sharing and communication globally using computers. 22 percent of the respondents were spending 21 or more hours for Entertainment weekly and 48 percent of the respondents were spending on the internet 13-20 hours for entertainment purposes per week. The average spending time of the respondents for entertainment was 16.01 hours per week which is more than the knowledge gaining time. A large portion (55percent) of the respondents sometimes took help from the

internet to solve various problems and 14 percent did that very often. It is recommended that the internet impact the personal life of the respondent positively and effectively. So the by using the internet, a person can be change and personality also change. More than half of 66 percent of respondents said there had some positive or negative impact of the internet on their personal life while 34 percent argued with that thinking. Since the birth of the internet, the number of people who use it increases each day, as do the number of hours that each person spends on it on average. 25 percent of the respondents thought that their behavior was changing because of the internet while 23 percent of respondents observed their behavior as usual and 35 percent were unchanged.

Technology can be the knowledge of techniques, processes, and the like, or it can be embedded in machines that can be operated without detailed knowledge of their workings. New technology knowledge is the knowledge of recent invented and coming technology. Almost all of the respondents; 97 percent believed that the internet is the source of acquiring new knowledge. 43 percent of the respondents sometimes feel that the internet is a waste of time while 22 percent very often realized that and 24 percent often. About 60 percent of respondents often think the internet helps in their study while 26 percent felt that very often. 79 percent of the respondent responded positively that they used the internet before the examination for study purposes while 21 percent had no dependency on the internet before the examination. 19 percent of the respondents sometimes checked out their daily lessons on the internet while 31 percent never depend on the internet.

Almost all the students (93 percent) were willing to provide extra cost for the internet. Generally, many countries see ICT (internet) as a gateway for the raising of educational standards as cited in (Albugamiand Ahmed, 2015). In 2007, the Saudi government invested almost 2 billion in reforming and improving education using modern technology. The heavy investment was made to introduce training and developmental programs for educators to ensure sufficient use of ICT in education and to facilitate learning for students.

Recommendations

The Parents/ Guardians of teenagers should monitor closely their children's SNSs usage. If possible, the parents should also join SNS so as to find out what actually happens on these sites. Teenagers need to be taught on controlled usage of social networking sites. So as not to rely heavily on SNSs. There is also a need to carry out more research to analyze the positive effects of social media, particularly social networking sites, on education since this research did not address this adequately. Teenagers should also be guided on how to balance SNSs interactions with face-to-face interaction so as not to miss out on the fundamentals of face-to-face interactions.

Conclusion

This benefit by increasing the communication skills with friends and relatives and it can develop their

socialization process more. Also, it can say that teenagers were able to use social media to obtain information about topics like health, education, and to increase the technical skills using the last technologies. Consequently, various forms of social media have changed the ways teenagers talk, learn, and think. On the other hand, teenagers are in danger of Facebook depression, cyberbullying, and online sexual harassment. It must be stressed that the benefits and risks of teenagers in the usage necessary to create parents' and teachers' “awareness” on the risks faced by pre-teenagers and of social media have a significant impact on their physical and psychological development. However, the studies in this direction are few and it suggests a wider study in Bangladesh on this issue.

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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